

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the forth regular issue in 2015. As always, I'd like to thank all institutions, reviewers and authors for their valuable support and work. Please consider yourself and encourage your colleagues to submit high-quality articles to our journal. I'd also like to further extend our editorial board: if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please do apply for a membership in our editorial board.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce 5 accepted papers from 6 different countries. In their collaborative work between colleagues from Brazil and Germany, Juliana de Melo Bezerra, Celso Massaki Hirata, and Dave Randall introduce and evaluate their conceptual framework for defining incentive mechanisms for virtual communities. Peter Fenwick from New Zealand focused on variable-length codes with constant hamming weights which extending work based on Goldbach conjecture to weight-3 and weight-4 codes. Gerald Senarclens de Grancy from Austria focuses in his work on an adaptive metaheuristic for vehicle routing problems with time windows and multiple service workers. In a comprehensive literature survey, Ani Grubišić, Slavomir Stankov, and Branko Žitko from Croatia cover aspects of adaptive courseware. Libor Polčák and Barbora Franková from the Czech Republic provide a summary of use cases and methods for clock-skew-based identification.

Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
Email: cguetl@iicm.edu